

SINGLE CARBON AND GLASS FIBRE TENSILE PROPERTIES AND THE CORRELATION WITH THEIR GEOMETRY

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ABSTRACT

Automated single fibre tensile tests were performed on carbon and glass fibres to characterise their tensile properties and cross-section accurately. An iterative compliance correction was developed to improve the strain accuracy. The results showed no correlation between tensile properties and the fibre cross-section but a clear dependency on the gauge length, lowering strength due to a higher defect probability in longer fibres. A dataset with more than 200 tests was obtained, which can be utilised to enhance simulation inputs and support predictive models for composite design.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced polymer composites (FRP) gain their mechanical performance primarily from the embedded fibres. These fibres carry most of the applied loads, thereby providing stiffness and strength to the composite parts. Accurate characterisation of these fibres is essential for understanding their role within composites and for predicting the mechanical behaviour of FRP products reliably. Classic composite simulations require properties such as the fibre diameter, the Young's modulus, the strength and the failure strain. Manufacturers provide such values, but typically only an average value and no distribution of the properties. They base their mechanical properties on impregnated bundle tests, not including the effect of fibre cross-sectional variation. In literature, fibre properties are commonly determined by single fibre tensile tests (SFTT). Those tests do allow for individual fibre cross-sectional area measurements, but care needs to be taken during handling and clamping [1, 2]. Other methods are single fibre fragmentation tests, loop tests and synchrotron radiation computed tomography on unidirectional composites [2].

Common reinforcements for FRPs are carbon and glass fibres. Given that those fibres are brittle materials influenced by the presence of manufacturing defects, they exhibit strength characteristics that are best described using probability models such as the Weibull distribution [3]. The classic Weibull distribution describes the weakest-link behaviour with a scale parameter and modulus. The scale parameter is the characteristic strength at which 63.2 % of the fibres will fail. The modulus, or shape parameter, reflects the variability in strength. A strong, reliable fibre is thus characterised by a high scale and shape parameter, respectively. The drawback of this distribution is that a large data set is required for accuracy. Several authors [2, 4] have confirmed that fewer than 100 tests introduce significant errors in the Weibull parameters.

An additional concern in SFTTs is the compliance correction. Depuydt et al.[5] and Engelbrecht-Wiggans et al. [6] have noted that the compliance correction methods suggested in the testing standards for single fibres are unable to correct the measured strain values adequately. Mesquita et al. [4] added that due to the non-linear tensile behaviour of the fibres, errors are introduced in the determination of the machine compliance. They applied an iterative compliance correction by updating the strain, which shifted the stress-strain diagram, and recalculating the compliance on the new strain range. They reported that the first iteration leads to a deviation of 11 % from the real machine compliance.

In the current study, SFTTs were performed on carbon and glass fibres to quantify their properties. Correlations between the mechanical properties and the geometry of the fibres, separated into the cross-section and the gauge length, will be analysed.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Fibre types

In this study, both carbon and glass fibres were tested. The carbon fibres are T700SC-12K-50C PAN-based fibres (Toray Industries, Japan) and the glass fibres are Advantex® R25HX14 E-CR fibres (3B Fiberglass, Belgium). Table 1 summarises the properties, as specified by the manufacturer.

Table 1: Fibre properties reported in their respective data sheet.

Material	Fibre type	Diameter [μm]	Tensile modulus [GPa]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Failure strain [%]
Carbon	T700SC-12K-50C	7	230	4900	2.1
Glass	Advantex® R25HX14	17-24	81-83	2700-2800	/

2.2 Automated single fibre tensile tests

The SFTTs were performed with the ALS1500-LEX820-FDAS770 device (Dia-Stron Limited, United Kingdom). The successive stages of this test are specimen preparation, dimensional measurements and mechanical testing, while the automated loading system with vacuum suction ensures transport of the specimens. More details on the functioning of the Dia-Stron device, as well as a comparison with single fibres mounted on card frames, were described by Islam et al. [7].

The fibres were meticulously extracted from the roving by hand. To limit the adhesion between fibres due to the sizing, the roving was first divided into smaller bundles, which were further separated with a fine brush. Each fibre was mounted onto two plastic end tabs fitted into the cassette slots. The cassette serves the purpose of specimen storage and facilitates specimen preparation. The slots in the cassette were spaced at a fixed length, predefining the gauge lengths of the fibres at 4, 12 and 30 mm. Alignment of the fibres was assured by V slits in the tabs and the precise rectangularity of both the tabs and slots. The fibres were glued in the tab with UV-curing adhesive (3099, Dymax Corporation, United States) at a wavelength of 365 nm for 15 s.

The dimensional measurement of the fibre was performed with the laser scanning micrometre (LSM-500S+6200, Mitutoyo, Japan) at an accuracy of 0.3 μm . The contactless measuring device was linearly calibrated between two reference fibres measured in the scanning electron microscope: 6.8-50.8 μm for carbon and 9.0-101.3 μm for glass. Calibrating each material independently ensured limited laser-material interaction on the diameter measurement. A 3D dimensional measurement was performed with approximately one longitudinal slice per 4 mm and three rotations per slice, with each approximately 220 points per rotation.

The mechanical testing of the fibre consisted of an SFTT in the extensometer with a 20 N load cell. A cross-head strain rate of 0.15 %/s was applied according to the ASTM C1557-14 standard. A gauge force of 0.5 mN was applied, and data were sampled every 100 ms.

2.3 Determination of fibre properties

The diameter measurements were filtered to remove erroneous measurements and noise [8]. Slices with an average diameter outside a range of 0.5-1.5 times the manufacturer's diameter were considered erroneous and automatically removed. The range for filtering the slice diameter was further refined to $\mu \pm 3\sigma$, with μ the mean and σ the standard deviation. Noise was removed by discarding individual data points deviating by more than 20 % of the average slice diameter. This filtering removed 6 % of

the measurements. The cross-sectional area was obtained from the surface integral in polar coordinates of the angular data points.

The acquired force-displacement curves were corrected for compliance in line with the ASTM C1557-20 standard. The SFTT at three different gauge lengths were plotted according to

$$\frac{\Delta L}{F} = \frac{l_0}{EA} + C_s \quad (1)$$

with ΔL being the recorded crosshead displacement, F the recorded force, l_0 the fibre gauge length, E the Young's modulus, A the cross-sectional area and C_s the system compliance. Fitting a straight line through the plot of $\Delta L/F$ as a function of l_0/A allows extracting C_s at the intercept (Figure 1a). The actual elongation of the fibre Δl can then be determined by

$$\Delta l = \Delta L - C_s F \quad (2)$$

This compliance correction is then applied iteratively by replacing the ΔL in equation 1 with Δl computed in equation 2, as suggested by Mesquita et al. [4]. To ensure that the iterative method converges, outliers were removed based on an interval of 100% around the mean value of the fitted slope. The system compliances obtained are 0.024 mm/N and 0.128 mm/N for glass and carbon, respectively (Figure 1b). Using the first iteration would cause a relative error up to 154 %.

Figure 1: Carbon compliance determination: (a) final compliance curve and (b) iteration.

Stress-strain curves with a load drop were discarded from the data analysis. A load drop is defined in this study as a difference of 5 mN between successive force measurements. When such a load drop occurred before reaching 25 % of the maximum force, it was considered linked to the tab slipping in the tensile grip, and the stress-strain curve was not discarded. The modulus was determined in the range of 0.1-0.6 % strain, according to the ISO 1566-1998 standard for fibres with a nominal failure strain above 1.2 %.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fibre properties

From the SFTTs, the diameter, tensile modulus, ultimate tensile strength, and failure strain for both fibre types were precisely computed (Table 2). The automation ensured large datasets of approximately 200 tests, which are vital for obtaining statistically accurate parameters [4]. The average diameter of both fibre types is in line with the value provided by the manufacturer. In addition to the average diameter, the cross-sectional shape was also measured. An ellipsoidal cross-section was measured for carbon fibres, in contrast with circular glass fibres (Figure 2), consistent with observations in the literature [1]. The modulus and ultimate tensile strength were lower than the values

provided by the manufacturer. However, those properties were measured with the impregnated bundle method and are thus difficult to compare.

Table 2: Fibre properties obtained from the single fibre tensile tests with a gauge length of 12 mm (mean \pm standard deviation).

Material	Number of tests	Diameter [μm]	Tensile modulus [GPa]	Ultimate tensile strength [MPa]	Failure strain [%]
Carbon	206	6.5 ± 0.3	226 ± 25	4571 ± 1092	1.75 ± 0.38
Glass	198	24.3 ± 1.4	72 ± 4	1625 ± 583	2.34 ± 0.87

Figure 2: Aspect ratio histogram: (a) carbon and (b) glass fibres.

3.2 Correlation between tensile properties and the cross-section

The interdependence between the tensile properties and the cross-section was studied with point clouds. The relation could be observed graphically from the point cloud orientation, and the coefficient of determination R^2 provides a quantitative evaluation of the linear fit. Low R^2 indicate a limited correlation. No correlation was observed between the tensile properties and the fibre diameter or aspect ratio (Figure 3), so the results for mechanical properties are believed to be unbiased. This confirms a previous study [4], where no correlation was found between the modulus and the fibre diameter for glass and only a slight negative correlation for carbon fibres.

Figure 3: Point clouds indicating the correlation between tensile properties (Young's modulus and ultimate tensile strength) and the fibre cross-section (diameter and aspect ratio) for carbon and glass.

3.3 Gauge length dependency

The interdependence between the tensile properties and the fibre length was studied with the Weibull parameters (Table 3). When comparing the 30 mm fibres to the shorter ones, an obvious gauge length dependency was found, stating that there is a higher probability of finding defects in the longer fibres, resulting in a lower Weibull scale parameter (Figure 4). The Weibull modulus appeared to increase with an increasing gauge length, representing more consistent fibres with a more uniform defect distribution. By representing the strength and strain with the Weibull distribution, apparent higher values were obtained than by averaging all the tests (Table 2). Besides having a higher tensile strength, carbon fibres were observed to have a higher Weibull modulus and thus being more consistent with a more uniform flaw distribution than glass fibres. Additionally, the importance of a large data set could be confirmed as the confidence intervals reduced with an increasing number of tests.

Table 3: Weibull parameters obtained from the single fibre tensile tests (mean and 95 % confidence interval).

Material	Gauge length [mm]	Number of tests	σ_0 [MPa]	m_{strength} [-]	ϵ_0 [%]	m_{strain} [-]
Carbon	4	55	5023 [4587, 5500]	3.1 [2.5, 3.8]	2.32 [2.14, 2.51]	3.2 [2.7, 3.9]
	12	206	4997 [4844, 5155]	4.6 [4.2, 5.1]	1.90 [1.85, 1.96]	5.1 [4.6, 5.7]
	30	60	3252 [3089, 3423]	5.2 [4.3, 6.3]	1.42 [1.34, 1.51]	4.6 [3.8, 5.4]
Glass	4	64	1591 [1454, 1740]	2.9 [2.4, 3.5]	2.60 [2.34, 2.89]	2.4 [2.0, 2.8]
	12	179	1827 [1740, 1917]	3.2 [2.8, 3.6]	2.62 [2.49, 2.75]	3.0 [2.6, 3.3]
	30	82	1208 [1107, 1319]	2.6 [2.2, 3.1]	1.48 [1.35, 1.62]	2.5 [2.2, 3.0]

Figure 4: Weibull probability functions as a function of the gauge length for carbon fibres: (a) strength and (b) strain.

4 CONCLUSION

SFTTs were performed on carbon and glass fibres to characterise their tensile behaviour. The fibre

diameter and aspect ratio were measured longitudinally and angularly with the laser scanning micrometre. The fibre modulus, ultimate tensile strength and failure strain were extracted from the stress-strain curve. No correlation was observed between the tensile properties and fibre cross-section. A gauge length dependency was found, though, for the Weibull strength and strain, as longer fibres have a higher probability of containing critical defects.

This comprehensive study on the tensile properties of single carbon and glass fibres provides a detailed input data set for simulations and facilitates the measurement of other fibre-dependent properties. Improving predictive models based on stiffness and strength will enable the development of enhanced designs for FRP parts.

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REFERENCES

- [1] F. Islam, S. Joannès, S. Bucknell, Y. Leray, A. Bunsell and L. Laiarinandrasana, Investigation of tensile strength and dimensional variation of T700 carbon fibres using an improved experimental setup, *Journal of reinforced plastics and composites*, **39**, 2020, pp. 144-162 (10.1177/0731684419873712).
- [2] Y. Swolfs, I. Verpoest and L. Gorbatikh, A review of input data and modelling assumptions in longitudinal strength models for unidirectional fibre-reinforced composites, *Composite Structures*, **150**, 2016, pp. 153-172 (10.1016/j.compstruct.2016.05.002).
- [3] W. Weibull, A statistical distribution function of wide applicability, *Journal of applied mechanics*, 1951, pp.
- [4] F. Mesquita, S. Bucknell, Y. Leray, S. V. Lomov and Y. Swolfs, Single carbon and glass fibre properties characterised using large data sets obtained through automated single fibre tensile testing, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **145**, 2021, pp. 106389 (10.1016/j.compositesa.2021.106389).
- [5] D. Depuydt, K. Hendrickx, W. Biesmans, J. Ivens and A. W. Van Vuure, Digital image correlation as a strain measurement technique for fibre tensile tests, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **99**, 2017, pp. 76-83 (10.1016/j.compositesa.2017.03.035).
- [6] A. E. Engelbrecht-Wiggans and A. L. Forster, Analysis of strain correction procedures for single fiber tensile testing, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **167**, 2023, pp. 107411 (10.1016/j.compositesa.2022.107411).
- [7] F. Islam, S. Joannès, S. Bucknell, Y. Leray, A. Bunsell and L. Laiarinandrasana, Towards accurate and efficient single fibre characterization to better assess failure strength distribution, *ECCM 18-18th European Conference on Composite Materials, Athens, Greece, 2018*, Paper pp. 7 p.
- [8] S. M. Delcourte, Enkelvoudige vezeltrekproeven om het Weibull gedrag van koolstof- en glasvezel te begrijpen, *Master's thesis*, KU Leuven, 2025.